

THE EUROPEAN GREEN DEAL AND ITS IMPACT ON THE RAW MATERIAL INDUSTRY

Vessela Petrova

University of Mining and Geology "St. Ivan Rilski", 1700 Sofia; E-mail: vessela.petrova@mgu.bg

ABSTRACT. Climate changes and environmental degradation are a threat to the existence of Europe and the world. To overcome these challenges, at the end of 2019, the European Commission outlined as a main political line the proposal for the European Green Deal. In most of its aspects, this document is a benchmark for a new mindset that aims to turn the EU in a fair and prosperous society with a modern, resource-efficient and competitive economy in which there will be no net greenhouse emissions in 2050 and the economic growth will not depend on the use of resources.

This publication reflects the path from the emergence of the idea of the European Green Deal to the policies pursued today. The academic papers developed in the field are analysed, as well as the prerequisites and challenges that lead to its implementation.

An attempt has been made to answer questions related to the main goals of the Green Deal and how these aims correspond to the raw material industry which will be the industry with the most significant consequences in the next decade.

Key words: European Green Deal, raw material industry

State of the art and development of the idea of a European Green Deal

From 1970 to 2017, annual global material extraction tripled continuing to grow and pose serious risks worldwide. About half of the total greenhouse gas emissions and over 90% of the biodiversity loss and water shortage are due to resource extraction and processing of materials, fuels and food. The EU industry has begun to change but it still accounts for 20% of the EU greenhouse gas emissions. It remains too "linear" and depends on the amount of new materials that are extracted, traded and processed into goods and eventually disposed as a waste material or emissions. Of the materials EU uses, only 12% are recycled (European commission, 2020).

To manage the climate change, the EU has already pursued a new policy. It is completely adapted to the climate change strategy that was announced in 1992. It was endorsed for the treaty on climate change aiming to limit the global warming to well below 2 degrees Celsius above the pre-industrial levels of the continent. In 2001 the EU succeeded in strengthening its values and becoming an international leader in terms of climate change when it was supported enough by the followers of the Kyoto protocol.

Furthermore, some ambitious policies backed up the European Union's role in the world (Siddi, 2020).

Figure 1 traces the dynamic development of sustainability strategies of the European Commission.

Fig. 1. Development of the idea of a European Green Deal

The European Green Pact provides an action plan aiming to increase resource efficiency by moving to a clean, circular economy, restoring biodiversity and reducing pollution. The plan specifies the necessary investments and the available financial instruments. It explains how to ensure a fair and united transition of economy.

The EU aims to be climate neutral in 2050. European Climate Law has been proposed to make this political

commitment a legal obligation. Achieving this goal will require action by all sectors of the EU economy, such as: investing in green technologies, supporting industrial innovation, introducing cleaner, cheaper and healthier forms of private and public transport, decarbonising the energy sector, improving the energy efficiency of buildings and working with international partners to improve environmental standards worldwide (Sikora, 2021).

Attitude of the European Green Pact towards the mineral resources industry

The raw material industry plays a central role in achieving sustainable development. The new European Green Deal is addressing all policy areas relevant to sustainable mining management: climate change, biodiversity, agriculture and desertification, including sustainable water management. Human wellbeing is necessarily at the core of the European policies. The industry will be in the focus of the green policies and at the same time, it will be the major challenge in front of us in the next years.

There is no doubt that the EU has taken this step to make the whole of Europe green and free of carbon. The current situation of the member-countries has predisposed a lot of opportunities in this way. The outbreak of COVID-19 and the climate crisis have already led the countries to think about the positive factor of the carbon elimination that will influence health and environment. The green transition to new technologies like renewable energy, stationary energy storage and e-mobility is dependent on the critical raw materials that include neodymium, cobalt, tungsten, niobium, tantalum, etc. (Claeys, 2019).

There are a lot of challenges in the way of the Green Deal implementation when it comes to raw mineral industry. Currently, the environmental and social impacts of extracting and processing resources from the earth are very high.

National Recovery and Sustainability Plan

The European Recovery and Resilience Facility will make 672.5 billion EUR of loans and grants available to support reforms and investments by Member States. To access the funds, each Member State shall create a National Recovery and Resilience Plan, covering the period 2021-2026, and drafted in co-operation with its regions (European Commission, 2021)

The green transition is at the forefront of the Bulgarian Recovery and Sustainability Plan, concentrating almost half

(47%) of the total projected costs. In this way, the country will contribute to the implementation of the Pan-European targets for gradual decarbonisation. In addition, efforts are focused on three main areas: (i) creating conditions for the accelerated introduction of renewable energy sources and hydrogen; (ii) enhanced actions to increase the energy efficiency of the economy; (iii) sustainable mobility (National Recovery and Resilience Plan of the Republic of Bulgaria, v. 1.2, 2021).

The ultimate objective of the Recovery and Resilience Plan is to facilitate economic and social recovery from the crisis caused by the COVID-19 pandemic so that the Member States are prepared for the green transition. In pursuit of this goal, the European Commission has grouped a set of measures and reforms that will not only restore the potential for economic growth but will also develop it by ensuring the resilience to negative external factors. This will allow, in the long run, achieving the strategic goal of the Commission for convergence of the economy and incomes to the EU-average ones. At the same time, the Plan lays the foundations for a green and digital transformation of the economy, in the context of the ambitious goals of the Green Deal.

The plans should give particular focus to answering challenges identified in the European Semester and contributing to sustainable growth. Indeed, every recovery and resilience plan must have a minimum of 37% expenditure related to green investments and reforms, supporting implementation of the European Green Deal (Interreg Europe, 2021).

The renewables, besides demonstrating the growth capacity, have become a very important energy source for industry.

Figure 2 illustrates a RMI's (Rocky Mountain Institute) study which presents renewables on mine sites, with cumulative commissioned capacity surpassing 1.7 GW, far beyond the 1.4 GW goal set for 2022 (Kirk and Cannon, 2020).

Fig. 2. Cumulative Commissioned Renewable Energy Capacity (Kirk and Cannon, 2020)

EU energy governance and the Green Deal from the perspective of the mining industry

Several innovative exploration techniques have been developed by projects of Horizon 2020 to find minerals and ores which can make Europe a climate-neutral continent. Thus, Europe will be with a better economy and sustainable energy resources. According to 6 of the highlighted cutting-edge projects of the EU, access to resources is one of the most essential and complicated questions in terms of the Green Deal accomplishment since its main aim is to make Europe a carbon-neutral continent by 2050 (Brodny, Tutak, 2020).

Moreover, the Commission has set a plan to raise the EU's ambition on reducing greenhouse gas emissions to 55% below the levels of 1990 by 2030. Defence sectors, mobility, renewable energy production, electric vehicles, mobile phones and other means that are taking part in the consumption of energy will be made carbon neutral by 2050 (CORDIS, 2021).

The transition of energy is defined by the International Renewable Energy Agency. It is a pathway for the world to enhance the global energy sector by decreasing the usage of fossil-based fuels to zero percent by the mid of this century. It is very obvious that the role of mining and usage of coal is very essential to overcome the energy demand but at the same time it causes the need for global energy transitions because of the warming effect around the whole world.

During the past few decades, the transitioning to low-carbon systems of energy has been underway. As a consequence, the renewable energy brings 72% of new global power capacity in 2019 (www.renewablesnow.com). At present it is expanding being a strategic tool of the regulations of the governments of

most EU countries. Other factors that help the development of the renewable energy sector are outcomes from the Paris agreement where incentives and other encouragements were set to make citizens more active in meeting the decarbonisation and goals of zero-carbon climate. Some other countries in the EU have transitioned the support schemes of the past into auctions to purchase power through agreements.

Figure 3 illustrates all 17 minerals, which are used for different applications in the energy sector. The analysis of World Bank compares the mineral demand coming from the 10 energy technologies under the 2-degree scenario of temperature raise (2DS) and compares it with 2018 production figures. Panel a provides the percentage increase in mineral demand based on 2018 production figures with the majority of demand coming from the minerals needed for batteries, specifically graphite, lithium and cobalt. These minerals will be needed at scales significantly beyond current production levels, by up to as much as five times. Panel b presents the annual absolute increase in mineral production up to 2050, with production figures being the highest for aluminium, graphite, and nickel. Graphite demand increases in both absolute and percentage terms since graphite is needed to build the anodes found in the most commonly deployed automotive, grid, and decentralised batteries. About 4.5 million tons of graphite is needed to be produced annually by 2050, or a cumulative of 68 million tons, while graphite demand increases by nearly 500 percent from 2018 production figures, demonstrating the critical role graphite plays in the clean energy transition, being used in Li-ion batteries, the most widely projected deployed battery technology (Hund, Porta, Fabregas, Laing, Drexhage, 2020).

Fig. 3. (a) Annual demand from energy technologies as percentage of production 2018, (b) Annual demand from energy technologies in 2050, in million tonnes (Hund, Porta, Fabregas, Laing, Drexhage, 2020)

Wind, thermal and especially photovoltaic technologies are more suitable for the Green Deal commitment of the EU. Illustrated by numbers of the specific renewable energy

technology, it means that the power capacity of 1 MW is equal to 3000 solar panels production. In the scenario of electric transportation and wind power, each turbine contains almost 3.5

tons of metal in the form of stainless steel, iron, copper, etc. About 83 kg of copper is required in an electric vehicle. In this way, the overall demand for niche and base minerals, originating from the clean energy technology manufacturing, will grow significantly. In particular, the expected increase in the consumption of metals such as graphite, lithium, cobalt, etc. will need to be significantly ramped up by more than 450 % by 2050 from 2018 levels - to meet demand from energy storage technologies (Hund, Porta, Fabregas, Laing, Drexhage, 2020).

The prospects of demands suggest some promising opportunities in resource-rich countries, prompting governments of different countries. One of them is Bolivia having ¼ of the world's resources of lithium. The Democratic Republic of Congo and Chile are taking in policy and investment options for support and development of mining industries that are highly considered in the global energy transition context (Siddi, 2020).

With the increased demand for materials, the research and innovation led by the European Union are funded under the largest ever European funding programme Horizon 2020. Exploration of minerals is usually conducted in search of rich ores that could be used in the industries and for commercial purposes. At the moment it is very complicated to estimate the availability of resources in the core of the earth due to the severity of mining operations (Jones, 2021).

The overall expenses of energy are to be estimated at approximately 30% of the total cash operating costs of companies operating in the mining industry. The percentage of consumed energy is about 32% in the form of electricity. It is to be noted that the financial aspect is usually a more considerable motive for most of the companies and together with the decreasing costs of renewable energy in the last decade, the integration of renewable technologies and sources in mining has been a considered and performed process in the past few years (Eurostat, 2021).

For a few years, the renewable energy has been the chosen power supply in cases where the cost of electricity is highly significant. It was mostly applicable for the case of mining in remote areas where the electricity cost from the grid are more substantial, as well as places suffering energy disruptions (Claeys, 2019).

Due to the change in climate conditions and the momentum of the industry and sources of renewable energy gaining awareness in the world, they have become more cost competitive than ever before. Different mining companies in the EU are expanding the share and interests in renewable energy sources for powering their operations in specific countries.

This is possible through agreements for power purchasing or joint ventures with companies providing power by purchasing certificates of renewable energy or by the mining company's own micro grid. Undoubtedly, the assessment made by different projects show that there is still a long way to 100% renewable energy projects in the EU. Some experts say that hybrid solutions are somehow very much competitive, providing 50% of the energy from renewables.

It is considered that the global greenhouse effect due to mining is about 4-7%. From this range one percent goes to the emissions of CO₂ in the atmosphere. The Environmental, Social, and Governance: ESG Risk Atlas issued by S&P Global Rating clearly shows a negative perception in the face of mining and metal operations in different countries. The average mining sector report index exemplifies a very similar picture. It shows that the mining industry has achieved only a piecemeal progress

in the advancement on the Sustainable Development Goals. The change in climate conditions is a threat also to the mining sector. Therefore, different countries of the EU have already started thinking about a way to stop it (Brodney, Tutak, 2020).

Mining industry has never ignored its responsibility of taking care of the environment. The technology advancement has already led industries and various power generation companies to automation which ensures less human involvement. Furthermore, hazardous operations are usually done through robots and computer applications. However, drilling and exploration use equipment for locating and extracting minerals and that requires a very precise approach, human interference and actual implementation.

Advancements in renewable energy technologies and the industry commitment are a precondition for some benefits to renewable energy companies and the mining sector. These are: less reliance on carbon-related fuels, vulnerable fluctuations of global pricing, reduction in carbon emissions and specific ones from mines that consume a huge amount of electricity.

Environmental satisfaction and social criteria are used for the measurement and sustainability of green credentials of the specific projects. Improved engagement of investors will shift the debt of the capital market to green and sustainable markets that comply with the SDG and ESG indicators.

The situation for Bulgaria

The Bulgarian economy is one of the most resource-intensive in the EU, lagging behind the Member States of the Community in terms of applying the principle of circular economy and implementing eco-innovation activities. The economy spends on average 3.5 times more energy resources per unit of GDP than the average energy consumption in the EU.

In the industry sector there is no significant improvement in energy efficiency. The reasons for this include the lack of significant changes in the industrial structure, as well as a significant improvement in terms of technologies used and production processes. As a result, the energy intensity of Bulgarian industry remains the highest in the EU, almost three times higher than the EU average. To a large extent, the same applies to the services' sector, where, however, the gap with the EU is smaller (2.5 times). Figure 4 illustrates the share of energy from renewable source in 2015 in % gross final energy consumption. Note the position of the Bulgaria as one of the better countries in the European class (Eurostat, 2021).

Bulgaria remains the most carbon-intensive EU Member State, as the intensity of greenhouse gas emissions in the Bulgarian economy is more than 4 times higher than the EU average with a positive but modest trend of shortening the gap in this regard in recent years. The energy sector is the largest source of greenhouse gas emissions in the country with over 70% of the total emissions in the country. Coal-fired thermal power plants account for almost half of the sector's emissions but do not have access to adequate infrastructure to allow them to change their fuel base.

The desire to decarbonise the economy necessitates large-scale reform of the energy sector in the country which in turn is associated with significant investment needs for phased replacement of fuel in power plants through the use of alternative environment friendly energy sources.

The EU's goal is to create opportunities to phase out the use of coal for electricity generation and to gradually replace the fuel

Fig. 4. Share of energy from renewable sources in 2015, in % gross final energy consumption (Eurostat, 2021)

base in thermal power plants in the country's coal regions through the use of alternative environment friendly energy sources. This will lead to a reduction and subsequent elimination of greenhouse gas emissions resulting from the production of electricity from solid fuels in these regions.

Conclusions

The agreement and the plan of the EU countries to lower the carbon emissions till 2050 can pose a challenge to the power sector requiring improvements to be made focused on the climate change. More or less, the processes related to the extraction of minerals and metals will be unavoidably explored also by the renewable energy technologies. The aim is to achieve a prominent change in the greenhouse effect in the EU. Except the geothermal energy, the production of hydro, wind and solar energy are well developed. District heating through geothermal energy, biomass and waste can and should be developed.

Unfortunately, Bulgaria lags behind the goals of the European Green Deal, but there is the potential for rapid progress. We have unique advantages that we could use, the funding for which we could receive via the Impact and Sustainability Plan.

References

Brodny J., Tutak M., (2020). The Use of Artificial Neural Networks to Analyse Greenhouse Gas and Air Pollutant Emissions from the Mining and Quarrying Sector in the European Union, *Energies*, 13(8), 1925.

Claeys G. S., Tagliapietra T., Zachmann G., 2019. How to make the European Green Deal work, *Bruegel Policy Contribution Issue*, 14.

CORDIS. (2021, Jan 17). Sustainable innovative solutions for mineral exploration. Retrieved from cordis.europa.EU:

<https://cordis.europa.eu/article/id/413488-metal-and-minerals-exploration>

Eurostat. (2021, Jan 18). Archive:Energy from renewable sources. Retrieved from ec.europa. EU:

[https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php/Energy from renewable sources](https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php/Energy_from_renewable_sources)

Hund K., Porta D., Fabregas T., Laing T., Drexhage J, 2020. Minerals for Climate Action: The Mineral Intensity of the Clean Energy Transition, World Bank Report.

Interreg Europe, 2021, https://www.interregeurope.eu/news-and-events/news/11056/green-transition-under-the-errf/?no_cache=1&cHash=a07829c25057a69c27b0c11cf6244b0d

Jones B. (2021, Jan 18). Opportunities and challenges of renewable power for miners. Retrieved from Crugroup.com: <https://www.crugroup.com/knowledge-and-insights/spotlights/2019/opportunities-and-challenges-of-renewable-power-for-miners/>

National Recovery and Resilience Plan of the Republic of Bulgaria, 2021 <https://nextgeneration.bg/14>

Siddi M., 2020. The European Green Deal: Assessing its current state and future implementation. Finnish Institute of International Affairs.

Sikora A., 2021. European Green Deal – legal and financial challenges of the climate change. *ERA Forum* 21, 681–697. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12027-020-00637-3>

European commission, 2020 https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/ip_20_420

European Commission, 2021 https://ec.europa.eu/info/business-economy-euro/recovery-coronavirus/recovery-and-resilience-facility_en <https://renewablesnow.com/news/renewables-bring-72-of-new-global-power-capacity-in-2019-693872/>